

ISSN 2350-1472

Vol. 3

No.5

March 2016

ARS - Journal of Applied Research and Social Sciences

Peer Reviewed and Referred **Fortnightly** International Journal

**International Society for Green,
Sustainable Engineering and Management**

(An autonomous Institute under Public Trust Act, Govt. of West Bengal)

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
PLANNING COMMISSION
Government of India

<p><i>Organizational Member</i> Quality Council of India Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion Government of India Ministry of Commerce & Industry</p>	<p><i>Key Patron</i> Indian Green Building Council (IGBC)- Confederation of Indian Industries (CII's)</p>
<p><i>Institutional Member</i> Indian Statistical Institute Academic institute of national importance as recognized by a 1959 act of the Indian parliament</p>	

INDEX

Serial	Title	Author	Pages
1	Effect of School Environment on Academic Performance of Higher Secondary Students	Sunaina Kaur Maanand Dinesh Nagar	1-19
2	Intra-state disparities- policy initiatives for balanced regional growth	Dr. S.P. Rajendran, Dr. M. Raghuram Murthy	20-32
3	Learning styles in English practiced by the students at secondary level and its influence on academic achievement in relevance with students of Chennai district.	T.K.Manimozhi	33-38
4	Political representation of backward classes in the panchayat raj institutions of Andhra Pradesh -- a case study of three local body elections (2001, 2006, 2014).	M. Akshuthanandh	39-50

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

Effect of School Environment on Academic Performance of Higher Secondary Students

Sunaina Kaur Maan* and Dinesh Nagar**

*Ph.D scholar, Department of Psychology, Barkatullah University, Bhopal. Mobile number 9826030773. Sunaina.july@gmail.com

1

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management
Recognized

Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

**** Professor, Department of Psychology, Barkatullah University, Bhopal. Mobile number 9425018754. dineshnagarbu@gmail.com**

Effect of School Environment on Academic Performance of Higher Secondary Students

ABSTRACT

The major objective of the present study was to construct and validate the school environment scale on outcome measures related to academic performance. One hundred and nineteen students enrolled in eleventh standard in an English medium CBSE school were randomly selected to participate in the present study. A large number of items based on the contemporary theoretical models of school environment were prepared to assess the student's perception of the school environment. The academic performance was assessed on the basis of CGPA scores and performance satisfaction of students. The principal components factor analysis performed on items pertaining to the school environment indicated evidence of six factors which were labeled as intellectual stimulation, encouragement, acceptance, rejection and control. All the six components of school environment failed to predict present academic performance and satisfaction level of performance relative to friends. On the other side cognitive encouragement was found to be positively correlated with satisfaction with one's present performance but was negatively correlated with past academic performance. The factor related to acceptance of student by teachers in the classroom setting was found to be positively correlated with students satisfaction with their own performance while rejection experienced by the students in the classroom setting was negatively correlated with students satisfaction with own performance. Finally, student's perception of loss of control significantly and adversely affected the student's present academic performance. The results of this study are explained within the context of

2

student's academic aspirations, his commitment to attend the full time coaching classes so as to compete in entrance examination for career and growth after higher secondary examination. Implications of the study are discussed.

Keywords: School Environment, Academic Performance, Intellectual Stimulation

Effect of School Environment on Academic Performance of Higher Secondary Students

Introduction

Worldwide education has become highly competitive. In the developing countries like India high academic performance particularly at higher secondary level is needed for admission in better courses at the college level and eventually better jobs after the completion of education. The entire education system seems to revolve around enhancing the academic achievement of students. Academic achievement has become a yardstick of self worth and success. Very often the outcome of education determines the quality of life, progress and job satisfaction of people (Mayuri & Devi, 2003). A large body of research has spelled out various reasons pertaining to low academic performance and high rates of failure which includes bad study habits, low IQ, faulty teaching methods, erroneous examination systems, social and economic disparities etc. The objective of the present pilot research is to explore the psycho-social factors embedded in the classroom setting which are related to academic performance of students who are in the eleventh standard.

A large number of Educational researchers have conducted studies focusing on major psycho-social factors embedded in the classroom and school settings contributing to academic

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

achievement, performance and success of students (Stevenson, & Lee, 1990., Falsario, Muyong, & Nuevaespana, 2014., Aknabi, 2014, Usaini & Abu Bakar 2015). Because of increased competition quality of performance has become the main goal of educational institutions. Increased expectation and attitudes of teachers, parents and institutions are found to be continuously creating a lot of pressure on students in particular and on the total education system itself in general. A number of factors are said to have contributed to the students poor academic achievement in school (Ajewole & Okebukola 2000). In recent years a large number of schools are devoting lot of time and energy by adapting different strategies to help the students to achieve better in their scholastic performance.

A large number of studies conducted on school climate have revealed that factors related with safe and orderly classroom environment, school facilities were significantly related to student's academic performance (Persaud & Turner 2008., Marsden 2005., Glassman 1994). Evidence exist that poor classroom facilities inhibit the students' ability to learn and creates a stressful set of working conditions for teachers. Physical, social and psychological factors embedded in the school environment like quality of classroom, libraries, laboratories, teachers' quality, attitude of the school management, teaching methodology are having close linkages with the students' academic performance and achievement (Ajayi, 2001., Oluchukwu, 2000). The physical factors characteristics of the school like poor lighting, noise, high levels of carbon dioxide in Classrooms and inconsistent temperatures adversely affect the teaching learning process and make teaching and learning difficult. Poor maintenance and ineffective ventilation systems lead to poor health among students as well as teachers, which leads to poor performance and higher absentee rates (Frazier, 2002 Lyons, 2001; & Ostendorf, 2001). In contrast when students perceive their school environment to be supportive and caring they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward themselves and pro-social attitudes and behaviors toward others (Schaps, Battistich, & Solomon 1997). Much of the available research shows that supportive schools foster positive outcomes including and promoting the students' sense of connectedness

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

and belongingness or community (Resnick et al. 1997., Baumeister & Leary 1995., Schaps, Battistich, & Solomon 1997) .

Freiberg (1998) argues that various aspects of school social climate like trust, respect, mutual obligation and concern for others welfare can have powerful effects on educators and learners' interpersonal relationships as well as academic achievement and overall school progress. Based on the recent study Wynne (1980) has pointed out linkage between that the value of good relationships and non-academic curricular events involving both teachers and students contribute to school coherence. In the school interaction among one group of students with other group members will influence his or her performance (Inyang-Abia 2001). Evidence exist that students who succeed in social relationships with their co-students have been found to be successful in their school work (Brembeeks, 1980). Duke and Perry (1978) also noted that good student-teacher relationships in alternative schools were associated with both a degree of informality and good behavior. A safe, caring, participatory and responsive school climate tends to foster great attachment to school as well as providing the optional foundation for social, emotional and academic learning (Blum et al., 2002. Berkowitz & Bier, 2005; Catalano et al., 2002; Greenberg et al. 2003).

Within this backdrop the present study was planned to examine the links between student perception of school environment and their academic performance. One of the main purposes of this study was to construct a brief school environment questionnaire and thereafter is to examine the relationship between components of school environment with student academic performance.

Method

SUBJECTS-

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management
Recognized

Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

One hundred and nineteen students from a co-ed English medium school who have passed high school from the CBSE board were randomly selected to participate in the present study. Survey questionnaire were distributed to 68 males and 51 females belonging to Science and Commerce stream of a senior secondary school. The students were comparable across major demographical variables like age and socio economic status.

Measures:

A brief survey instrument was prepared. In the first section of the survey the respondents were required to furnish their demographical information like age, sex, socio economic status and so forth. In the second section the items on school environment were prepared while the last section was devoted to record the student's objective performance and performance satisfaction. A brief description of the measures is given below:

Demographic Information: Items in this section were related to understand the background information about the respondents. Some of the items were related to age, gender, degree of choice in selection of subjects in the standard eleventh and so forth.

Assessment of school environment: To assess the perceived school environment the researcher consulted a number of related standard scales (Mishra, 2012, Moos & Insel, 1974). Based on the contemporary theoretical models a large number of items on different component of school environment were prepared. The items were focused on assessing the academic and creative stimulation, patterns of interaction between teachers and students, maintenance of discipline in the classroom, encouragement given by the teachers and so forth.

Assessment of Academic Performance: To assess the objective and subjective performance the respondents were required to report their CGPA in their tenth and eleventh standard. The

students were also asked to rate their level of satisfaction with their own performance and performance satisfaction relative to their friends.

Procedures:

A brief survey instrument was distributed in the classroom setting. The students from biology, mathematics and commerce stream were selected at random and were asked to assemble in their respective classes. The researcher read the instructions loudly and thereafter explained the details regarding the manner in which responses were to be recorded. For instance, the respondents were told to read the items presented in section 2 one by one and carefully record their responses on a five point scale. The participants were assured that their responses will be completely confidential and anonymous and that no individual questionnaire would be shown to school authorities.

Result

Factor analysis

The participant's responses on the seventy items of the school environment inventory were subjected to a principal component factor analysis using Keiser's criterion of factor extraction. The rotated factor loading indicated evidence of five factors having an Eigen value more than one. In the order of extraction the factors were labeled as intellectual stimulation, encouragement, acceptance, permissiveness, rejection, and control. A brief description of these component scales are given below:

- 1- Intellectual stimulation:** The items which showed high loading on the first factor were summed together to give this five item subscale. Items pertaining to intellectual stimulation were characterized by the teachers multiple ways to explaining the subject matter to students, asking questions, enhancing motivational levels of students and so forth. The scores on this scale ranged from 5 to 25 where high scores indicate the high intellectual stimulation.

- 2- **Encouragement:** This three item subscale implies good atmosphere for study in the school and get the motivation to work hard. This factor measures teacher praise the students with higher educational ability. Range of this score is 5 to 15. High score in this item scale represents a high degree of encouragement.
- 3- **Acceptance-** This subscale consists of one item which ranges 5 shows teachers participation with students in different co-curricular activities.
- 4- **Permissiveness -**This subscale consists of one item with range of 5. It measures that students can do anything prior to the permission of the teacher.
- 5- **Rejection-** This subscale consists of six items. It measures the teacher gives physical punishment and if they not complete their work, not allow sitting in class, teacher is not worried about poor marks of the students, they are not pay attention when they do not want the answer the question, relationship between teacher and student is not good. Teachers give physical punishment. The score on this scale range 5 to 30 where high scores indicate rejection of the students.
- 6- **Control:** This component of school environment is comprised of single item which-this factor consist that while preparing the rules of institution the opinion of the students should be considered. Range of this score is 5.

Table 1: Principal Component Factor analysis indicating loadings on the school environment items

s.no.	Items no.	C o n t r o l

		n t s o f S c h o o l E n v i r o n m e n t					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
1.	Teachers give physical punishment to students.	.09	-.29	-.06	-.09	.48	.02
2.	Students can freely express their point of which is different from teachers.	.15	.02	-.03	.09	.51	.08
3.	Often the Teachers explain the major concepts by citing relevant examples.	.43	.24	.12	.35	-.27-	-.13
4.	Students can do anything prior to the permission from teachers.	-.28	.08	.04	.47	.19	.11
5.	While imposing the major rules of the school the opinion and suggestions of students are considered.	.15	-.01	.25	-.19	.18	.62

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

6.	The academic atmosphere of the school is encouraging.	.19	<u>.69</u>	.11	.15	-.14	-.08
7.	Teachers while teaching give several examples related to the life situations.	<u>.46</u>	.21	.39	.17	-.08	-.30
8.	Teacher taught relationship is not friendly.	-.12	-.16	.15	-.04	<u>.46</u>	-.02
9.	Teachers inspire the students to work hard.	.31	<u>.58</u>	.12	.28	-.22	-.09
10.	Teachers participate with students in different co curricular activities.	.08	.12	<u>.63</u>	.12	.07	.003
11.	Teachers do not generate interest in their students.	-.23	-.18	-.15	-.01	<u>.40</u>	-.01
12.	When teachers do not wish to the answer the questions of student, then they do not pay attention to the opinion of students.	-.02	-.12	-.16	.10	<u>.61</u>	.002
13.	Teachers encourage the students to write their answers themselves.	<u>.49</u>	.20	.19	.17	.14	.11
14.	Teachers ask method to solve the important problems.	<u>.57</u>	-.01	.12	.35	.03	.03
15.	Teachers praise the students with higher educational ability.	.26	<u>.51</u>	.08	.08	.08	.34
16.	Teachers ask several questions to students while teaching.	<u>.50</u>	.05	.08	.20	.006	.17
17.	When students get poor marks in one subject then teacher do not worry about it.	-.29	.01	-.05	-.16	<u>.47</u>	.07
		5	3	1	1	6	1

Table 2: Correlation analysis depicting relationship between components of school environment with Academic Performance

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

	Components of school Environment	Encouragement	Acceptance	Permissiveness	Rejection	control
	Intellectual stimulation					
Present academic performance	-.067	-.144	-.046	-.123	-.072	-.145
Past academic performance	-.090	-.196*	-.169	-.146	.079	-.13
Influence of choice	.163	.091	.061	.189*	-.188*	-.057
Satisfaction with one's self	.130	.214*	.193*	.011	-.185*	.030
Satisfaction level while comparing with others	-.027	-.091	-.037	-.127	-.041	-.077

*.01 significant

Correlation analysis-

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

In order to predict the relationship of school environment with academic performance a correlation analysis was performed. The result of correlation analysis presented in table 2 revealed that of all the five components of school environment intellectual stimulation and Encouragement and rejection were found good predictor of components of academic performance. In contrast acceptance and control failed to predict academic performance. The result further revealed that cognitive encouragement component of school environment predicted the past academic performance satisfaction with performance relative to one's self. In other words students exhibiting high cognitive encouragement and permissiveness reported better performance. All the six components of school environment failed to predict present academic performance and satisfaction level of performance relative to friends. On the other side cognitive encouragement was found to be positively correlated with satisfaction with one's present performance but was negatively correlated with past academic performance. The factor related to acceptance of student in the classroom setting was found to be positively correlated with students satisfaction with their own performance while rejection experienced by the students in the classroom setting was negatively correlated with students satisfaction with own' performance. Finally, student's perception of loss of control significantly and adversely affected the student's present academic performance.

Discussion and Conclusion-

One major objective of the present study was to develop school environment scale. The factor analysis results indicate evidence of five underlying dimensions labeled as: intellectual stimulation, encouragement, permissiveness, rejection and control. Indeed several recent studies investigating variables relating to school social variables have found significant associations with performance (Brookover et al., 1979; Rutter, Maughan, & Mortimore, Ouston & Smith, 1979). These effects have revealed significant, consistent relationship with variables defining teacher performance (Brophy, 1979; Centra & Potter, 1980; Glasman & biniaminov, 1981; Good, 1979;

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

Purkey & Smith, 1983; Stockard & Maybery, 1985). Our result is contradictory with these researches, a large number of students are attending coaching classes in 11 standard because they make their minds for competitive exams and the level of studies in coaching is much higher than school. And they are not willing to go to school. But they are forced to come to school with few reasons, (attendance, and practical.) and teachers are not encouraging the students for their academic so they perceive rejection. Overall what we found that psycho- social environment of school is not good. There exists significant positive of correlation between achievement in chemistry and overall school environment of higher secondary students.(Beulahbel Bency, P. B. & Krishna Prasad (2013). But this finding contradicts with the study of Arul Lawrence, A. S. & Vimala, A. (2012).it is important to note that when healthy teacher-taught relationship exists in school. In this study we found level of rejection is significant which shows teacher taught relationship is not good which goes a long way in the promotion of learning among students and this enables them to share knowledge and experience that will enhance the better school environment (Sunday, A.A 2012).several researches are supported this study. Some of researchers revealed that the school environment has a significant influence on academic performance (Laurence & et.al.,Danial et.al.2014,Orlu, c2013, Eric, C.2005, Owarye,J.S. 2011 Antaka 2013.) . Result shows that there is correlation between encouragements with satisfaction level of performance of the person. The results of this study are explained within the framework of student's academic aspirations to compete in entrance competitive examination after completion higher secondary examination.

References

- Ajewole, G.A. & Okebukola, F. O. (2000). *Improving socio cultural aspect of classroom learning environment in enhancing students performance in biology*. In Annual Conference proceeding of science Teachers Association of Nigeria (ppl 127 -130). Jos: HEBN Publishers Plc.
- Aknabi, M.I. (2014) Classroom climate and academic Performance among female student in Asa Government Rea , Kwara state.
- Biniaminov, I & Glassman, N.S. (1981). Second determinants of students achievement in secondary school education. *American Educational Research Journal* 20 (2): 251 – 268.
- Brookover, W., Beady, C., Flood, P., Schweitzer, J., & Wisenbaker, J. (1979). *School social systems and student achievement :schools can make a difference*. New York :Praeger.
- Brophy, j. (1979). Teacher behavior and its effects. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 71, 733-750
- Battistich, V., & Hom, A. (1997). *The relationship between students' sense of their school as a community and their involvement in problem behaviors*. *American Journal of Public Health*, 87(12), 1997–2001

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

- Baumeister, R., & Leary, M. (1995). *The need to belong: Desire for interpersonal attachments as a fundamental human motivation*. *Psychological Bulletin*, 117(3), 497–529
- Berkowitz, M. W. & Bier, M. C. (2005). *What works in character education: A report for policy makers and opinion leaders?* (Character Education Partnership). Retrieved on: May 6 2010, from http://www.character.org/atf/cf/{77B36A C3- 5057-4795-8A8F 9B2FCB86F3EB }/practitioners_518.pdf
- Bilbao, et al. (2012). *The teaching profession*. Metro Manila: Lorimar Publishing Co., Inc.
- Brookover, W. B., & Lezotte, L.W. (1979). Changes in school characteristics coincident with changes in student achievement (executive summary). Paper No.17. Michigan State University, Institute for Research on Teaching
- Catalano, R. F., Berglund, M. L., Ryan, J. A. M., Lonczak, H. S., & Hawkins, J. D. (2002). *Positive youth development in the United States: Research findings on evaluations of positive youth development programs*. *Prevention & Treatment*, Vol. 5,15. Retrieved May 6, 2010 from <http://journals.apa.org/prevention/volume5/ pre0050015a.html>.
- Devi, s. & Mayuri,.K. (2003). The effects of family and school on the Academic Achievement of Residential school children. *Journal o Community Guidance and Research* 20 (2): 139-149.

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

Falsario, H.N., Muyong, R.F., & Nuevaespana (2014) *Classroom Climate and Academic Performance of Education Students*, De La Salle university, manila Philippines .

Freiberg, H. J. (1999) *School Climate: Measuring, Improving and Sustaining Healthy Learning Environments* (Philadelphia, PA: Falmer Press).

Freiberg, H. J. and Stein, T. A. (1999) Measuring, improving and sustaining healthy learning environments, in: H. J. Freiberg (ed.) *School Climate: Measuring, Improving and Sustaining Healthy Learning Environments* (Philadelphia, PA: Falmer Press), p. 11

Glasman, N. s., & Biniaminov, I. (1981). Input- Output analyse of schools. *Review of Educational Research*, 51, 509-539

Hawkins, J. D., Catalano, R. F., Kosterman, R., Abbott, R., & Hill, K. G. (1999). *Preventing adolescent health-risk behaviors by strengthening protection during childhood*. *Archives of Pediatric and Adolescent Medicine*, 153, 226–234.

McNeely, C., Nonnemaker, J., & Blum, R. (2002). *Promoting school connectedness: Evidence from the National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent Health*. *Journal of School Health*, 72, 138–146.

Moos, R.H. & Insel, P.M. (Eds.). (1974). Systems for assessment and classification of human

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

environment: an overview. Palo Alto, California: National Press Books.

Mors, R.H. & Moos, B.S. (1978). Classroom social climate and student absences and grades

Journal of Educational Psychology, 70, 263-269.

Purkey, S.C., & Smith, M.S. (1983). Effective schools: A review. *The Elementary School Journal*, 83, 427-452.

Rutter, M., Maughan, B., Mortimore, P., Ouston, J., & Smith, A. (1979). *Fifteen thousand hours secondary schools and their effects on children*. Cambridge; Mass.: Harvard University Press.

Resnick, M. D., Bearman, P. S., Blum, R. W., Bauman, K. E., Harris, K. M., Jones, J., Tabor, J.,

Beuhring, T. Sieving, R. E., Shew, M., Ireland, M., Bearinger, L. H., & Udry, J. R. (1997).

Protecting adolescents from harm: Findings from the National Longitudinal Study on Adolescent Health. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 278(10), 823-832.

Schaps, E., Battistich, V., & Solomon, D. (1997). School as a caring community: A key to

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management
Recognized

Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

character. In A. Molnar (Ed.), *The construction of children's character*. Ninety-sixth yearbook of the National Society for the Study of Education (pp. 127–139). C National Society for the Study of Education.

Schaps, E., Battistich, V. & Solomon, D. (2004). Community in school as key to student growth: Findings from the Child Development Project. In J. Zins, R. Weissberg, M. Wang, & H. Walberg (Eds.), *Building academic success on social and emotional learning: What does the research say?* New York: Teachers College Press

Stevenson, H.W., & Lee, S. (1990). Contexts of achievement. *Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development*, 55, 1-106.

Stevenson, H.W., & Lee, S. (1990). Contexts of achievement. *Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development*, 55, 1-106.

Stockard, j., 7 Mayberry, m. (1985). *Learning environments: A review of the literature on school environments and student achievement* (final report). Washington, DC: National

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering and Management

Recognized
Voluntary Organization
(Research, Development & Training)
Planning Commission
Government of India

Institute of Education.

Tagiuri, R. (1968). The concept of organizational climate. In R. Tagiuri & R.H.Litwin(Eds).

Organizational climate: Exploration of a concept. Boston: Howard University division of Research, Graduate school of Business Administration.

<https://www.facebook.com/ISGSEM>

ARS - Journal of Applied Research and Social Sciences

WELCOME

ISSN 2350-1472

International Society for Green, Sustainable Engineering & Management

**(An Autonomous Institute Registered under Public Trust Act., Govt of West Bengal)
Publishes**

ARS - Journal of Applied Research and Social Sciences

A fortnightly/semi-monthly (2 issues per month) print journal publishing research based articles chosen from all over India and abroad.

It deals with potential topics in applied research in all disciplines of social sciences and management.

Author guidelines:

- Title and headings of the article would be **BOLD, UPPERCASE & CENTRE** aligns.
- **Affiliation:** Author should mention his affiliation (University/College etc) and present address of communication with mobile and email.
 - Body of the article would be 12 points size and Times new remain fonts.
 - Send **FULL ARTICLE** to the email address below.
 - After getting acceptance email, send the full article
 - One copy of print journal will be sent to the first author /Communicating author.

Hard copy Article should be sent to:

Mrs.Sonali Chaudhuri
C/o Dr.Debaprayag Chaudhuri
94, Garfa Main Road, Ground Floor,
Jadavpur,Kolkata-700 075,WB
(M) 9674766180

Chairman of ISGSEM

Dr.Debaprayag Chaudhuri
Researcher
Email:debaprayag@gmail.com

Treasurer of ISGSEM

Mrs.Sonali Chaudhuri
Economic Consultant
Email:sonali.chaudhuri2014@gmail.com

Every Communication should be done to:

The Secretary ISGSEM
Email: Secretary.isgsem@yahoo.in,
isgsem.research.kolkata@gmail.com

ISSN: 2350-1472

